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Productivity of Pulse Crops in Northern Kerala's Summer Rice Fallows

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The predominant rice-based farming method in northern Kerala, especially in Kasaragod, Kannur, and Kozhikode districts, is rice-rice-fallow. Therefore, to determine the suitability of various pulse crops (cowpea, black gram, green gram and red gram) for summer fallows of double-cropped lowland rice fields under varying nitrogen doses, a field study was conducted at the Regional Agricultural Research Station, Pilicode, Kerala, India. Number of branches per plant at 100 and 75 % recommended dose of nutrients (RDN) (9.40 and 9.93 respectively), leaf area index (LAI) at 100 and 50 % RDN (1.16 and 1.28 respectively), crop growth rate (CGR) (4.57 g m⁻² per day) and yield at 50 % RDN (1681.16 kg ha⁻¹) was significant for cowpea. Cowpea and red gram performed better among the different pulses regarding yield.

Keywords: sustainability; fallow; pulse; *Subhiksha Keralam*, lowland, rice; summer crop